

Theatrical forest excursions

Introduction

Consultation between the various players in the five areas that have signed a Forestry Territory Charter (CFT) in Normandy has highlighted the need for coordinated action between players, as well as the need to explain what is being done in the forest. The aim of EUROFORNORM was therefore to create and run a regional network of forest areas in Normandy. "The future of Normandy's forests in the face of climate change" emerged as one of the priority themes.

Methodology and results

The EUROFORNORM project has held a number of meetings in the field, with the aim of raising awareness among a wider audience of the issues associated with the consequences of climate change and the anticipated changes in the region's forests, and encouraging them to express their views, understand their expectations of the forest, and be the driving force behind proposals for the future of local forests. The operational group decided to create and organise dramatised outings followed by debates. These two-hour outings were equally divided between the theatrical performance and the debate between the participants. The theatrical performance, via a pedestrian circuit illustrating certain points with concrete visuals, made it possible to bring out certain points of view, but also to accentuate various character traits of the actors or to make the participants think through the prism of humour. The participants were then encouraged to express themselves and listen to each other, and were able to collectively highlight their points of agreement and disagreement. Two complementary models of outings, one on the future of hardwoods in the context of climate change and the other on the future of biodiversity, were developed and organised in 4 different areas of Normandy.

Lessons learned

These outings provided an opportunity to discuss the impact of climate change, how climate change effects can be anticipated and how forests can be adapted, the expectations of the public and the actions and commitments they can undertake. They provided an opportunity to explain the forest of today and the current methods used to try to anticipate and mitigate climate change.

These innovative meetings were very well received, with over 150 people attending and participating. These initiatives have also been the subject of regional communications through articles and reports, confirming the general public's interest in this type of subject.

Figure 1. Outing in a forest area of Normandy held within the EUROFORNORM project.

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Further information

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/euro-fornorm-14-50-61-emergence-and-animation-innovative-and-operational-network-normandy_en

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